

A Comprehensive Review of Electrochemical Membrane Bioreactors for Enhanced Pollutant Removal and Fouling Mitigation

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Suggested Citation

Azimi, S., Wang, B. & Eheneden, I. (2024). A Comprehensive Review of Electrochemical Membrane Bioreactors for Enhanced Pollutant Removal and Fouling Mitigation. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(3), 409-429.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(3\).33](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).33)

Abstract:

Membrane fouling significantly decreases the effectiveness and efficiency of Electrochemical Membrane Bioreactors (eMBRs). Foulants accumulate on membrane surfaces, affecting hydraulic permeability, electrochemical kinetics, microbiological activity, and mass transfer processes, resulting in decreased wastewater treatment performance by eMBRs and lower resource recovery efficiency. Therefore, this review focuses on examining electrochemical and membrane bioreactor technologies for wastewater treatment, with an emphasis on the influence of membrane fouling on eMBRs. The review explores various factors such as current density, electrode

materials, and operating conditions, and their effects on treatment efficiency. The integration of electrochemical processes with MBR shows improved removal of organic pollutants, nitrogen, and phosphorus, along with reduced membrane fouling and enhanced operating stability. The study advocates for careful electrode material selection to optimize energy consumption and pollutant removal. Further research is recommended to refine processes, address challenges, and explore resource recovery within eMBRs.

Keywords: *Electrochemical membrane bioreactors, Pollutants removal, Membrane fouling, Electrocoagulation, Electro-oxidation.*

Introduction

The integration of biological and filtration processes in MBR technologies represents a significant advancement in wastewater treatment, offering superior effluent quality, elevated sludge concentration, and minimized

sludge yield (Ensano et al., 2016). Despite its effectiveness, membrane fouling remains a prominent challenge, attributed to factors such as membrane properties, sludge characteristics, and operational conditions (Iorhemen, Hamza, & Tay, 2016). To address this issue, researchers have proposed various techniques, including

eMBRs technology, which integrate electrochemical processes with traditional MBRs. (Y.-K. Wang, Sheng, Shi, Li, & Yu, 2013; Y. Wang, 2020). The application of electric currents in eMBRs induces reactions that convert organic pollutants into simpler substances, leading to more effective fouling reduction and pollutant removal (Mendes Predolin, Moya-Llamas, Vásquez-Rodríguez, Trapote Jaume, & Prats Rico, 2021; Millanar-Marfa et al., 2018). These electrochemical processes, such as electrophoresis and electro-flocculation, minimize fouling and pollutant removal costs, contributing to the economic feasibility of eMBRs (Tognia et al., 2023; R. Zhang et al., 2023). Research by (Lifen Liu, Liu, Gao, Yang, & Chellam, 2012), demonstrates the significant mitigation of membrane fouling and enhancement of treatment efficacy through the imposition of electric fields in MBRs.

The characteristics of membrane materials such as; electrical conductivity, high permeability, mechanical stability, selectivity, and surface charge (Ensano et al., 2016) along with types of electrode materials such as; Fe, Cu, Al, stainless steel (SS), and Ti are considered as crucial factors of eMBR configurations (Karimi, Hazrati, Gharibian, & Shokrkhar, 2021; R. Zhang et al., 2023) with their selectivity directly influencing the eMBR performance in pollutants removal and membrane fouling mitigation. studies have indicated that the use of different types of membrane materials and electrode configurations is determined by specific electrochemical reactions, pollutant characteristics, energy recovery goals, and economic considerations (Asif, Maqbool, & Zhang, 2020).

On the other hand, optimization of operating conditions can further support the mechanism of pollutants removal and efficient mitigation of membrane fouling in eMBR. For instance, adjusting hydraulic retention time (HRT) and solid retention time (SRT), can increase the contact time of microorganisms with pollutants, thus amending the treatment efficacy (Asif et al., 2020), while regulating current density (CD) influences microbial activity and the movement of inorganic ions resulting to better mitigation of

membrane fouling (Y. Liu et al., 2023), likewise, retaining the proper pH level optimizes the electrochemical reactions and microbial activity leading to effective breakdown of substrate and membrane fouling mitigation (Mohanakrishna, Abu-Reesh, & Pant, 2020).

This review endeavors to investigate recent research on eMBRs, with particular emphasis on their configuration, efficacy, fouling mitigation, and electrochemical mechanisms. The examination of these aspects is motivated by the necessity to thoroughly elucidate the spatial arrangement of membrane components, methodologies for applying electric fields, and the intricate relationship between alterations in sludge properties and fouling phenomena. Such endeavors aim to enhance our comprehension of this innovative technology and expedite its practical implementation in wastewater treatment applications.

Methodology

This review includes a precise research analysis of peer-reviewed articles, scientific papers, and technical reports from databases such as SCOPUS, Google Scholar, and Web of Science. The selection criteria focused on electrochemical MBRs, fouling mitigation strategies, and wastewater treatment technologies. To discover the key findings, trends, and gaps in the literature, data extraction and synthesis were performed providing a solid foundation for analysis and discussion in this review. The illustrations in this article were precisely drawn utilizing MS. Power Point software to present a scientific clarity helping in better understanding of the related contents.

Basic Principles of eMBRs

Configurations

In eMBR systems, key components include a membrane module, an electrochemical reactor, and a bioreactor tank.

The electrochemical reactor, equipped with crucial electrodes, facilitates the elimination of

suspended particles and organic contaminants through electrocoagulation and electrooxidation processes. (Du et al., 2021). eMBRs typically have three configurations based on the membrane module's positioning relative to the electric field: outside the electric field, between two electrodes, or as an electrode itself (M. Wu, Liu, Gao, & Sillanpää, 2021). The positioning of electrodes affects sludge characteristics, altering Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS) content via electric field application. This alteration enhances fouling mitigation. When electrodes are within the membrane, an electrostatic repulsion force is generated, deterring foulants from adhering to the membrane surface and improving fouling resistance (M. Chen et al., 2023). (Figure 1) illustrates these eMBR configurations.

Membrane Materials

The significance of electrochemical membrane materials in wastewater treatment, highlighted by (Ensano et al., 2016), lies in their distinctive attributes defining efficacy within eMBRs. These attributes include electrical conductivity (Y.-K. Wang et al., 2013), high permeability, mechanical stability, selectivity, and surface charge (Ensano et al., 2016).

Porous membranes within the membrane module, such as polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) (Y. Shi et al., 2023), hollow fiber hydrophilic polyether sulfone (H-PES) (Moazzem, Ravishankar, Fan, Roddick, & Jegatheesan, 2020), ceramic, (R. Wang et al., 2023), graphene-based membranes (B. Li et al., 2023), and a range of others such as polymeric membranes and composite membranes, (Han et al., 2023) play a crucial role in separating treated water from sediments and pathogens (Goh, Ng, Lau, & Ismail, 2015). (Qi et al., 2020) demonstrated the superior removal efficacy of pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs) using a ceramic membrane in an electrochemical ceramic membrane bioreactor (ECMBR), emphasizing its potential for pollutant removal. Recent publications suggest that while membrane materials may not substantially affect pollutant removal, they positively impact membrane fouling mitigation (Asif et al., 2020).

Thus, membrane materials in eMBR plays important role in separation of pollutants from treated wastewater while improving membrane fouling mitigation based its distinct attributes as described.

Figure 1. Schematic Representation of eMBRs Configuration; Membrane Outside the Electric Field (a), between Two Electrodes (b) and as an Electrode Itself (c)

Electrode Materials

Electrode materials play a crucial role in optimizing the performance of eMBRs, with options such as Fe, Cu, Al, stainless steel (SS), and Ti being widely studied, (Karimi et al., 2021; R. Zhang et al., 2023). The selection of electrode materials depends on factors like specific electrochemical reactions, pollutant characteristics, energy recovery goals, and economic considerations (Asif et al., 2020). Researches have introduced novel electrode materials to improve eMBR efficiency and address challenges such as membrane fouling, erosion, and energy consumption.

The introduction of Fe rod electrodes into continuous electrocoagulation (EC) reactors showed enhanced removal efficiency for color, soluble chemical oxygen demand (COD), and turbidity (Abbasi, Zinatizadeh, Mirghorayshi, Zinadini, & McKay, 2022). Notably, Fe-Al electrode combinations outperformed others, achieving significant pollutant reduction and lower energy consumption (Sharma, Prabhakar, Tiwari, Dhar, & Halder, 2021). Additionally, a needle-like Cu-Fe₃O₄@Fe electrode demonstrated efficient mass and electron transfer, with exceptional stability and low leaching rates for Cu and Fe (Z. Zhang et al., 2023). These findings highlight the promising potential of various electrode materials in enhancing wastewater treatment processes.

Meanwhile, some studies have demonstrated the performance variations of electrode materials in

eMBRs explaining the need for developing electrode material that helps keeping balance between efficiency and availability. In the treatment of diluted N, N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC) wastewater using bio-electrochemical systems combined with anaerobic digestion (BES-AD), stainless-steel cathodes, particularly SSM-100 m, exhibited superior performance in COD removal and membrane fouling mitigation (Xie et al., 2021).

However, while electrode material advancements like Ti/RuO₂-Sb₂O₄ have improved electrochemical oxidation, practical implementation may encounter challenges such as material availability, synthesis complexity, and long-term stability (Salazar-Banda, Santos, Duarte Gonzaga, Dória, & Barrios Eguiluz, 2021). On the other hand, in anodic eMBRs, electrode material choices differ due to their impact on electrooxidation processes (M. Chen et al., 2023). These findings underscore the need for further research on developing novel electrode materials to address the mentioned challenges.

Overall, careful selection of electrode materials is vital for optimizing various electrochemical methodologies, including electrocoagulation, eMBRs, and bio-electrochemical systems, resulting in improved pollutant removal, reduced energy consumption, and enhanced operational stability. Some instances of studied electrode materials studies in different researches for wastewater treatment are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Examples of Studied Electrode Materials for Wastewater Treatment

Electrode materials	Pros	Cons	Pollutants removal performance	References
Ti/SnO ₂ -Nb ₂ O ₅	High efficiency in COD and color removal	-	Best performing material	(Y. Wang, 2020)
Graphite felt	Supports microbial growth, suitable filtration, high water quality	Limited catalytic activity	Good option to be used as anode electrode	(Y.-K. Wang et al., 2013)
carbon felt-incorporating stainless-steel mesh	Effective in producing a micro-electric field- Encourages microbial	Specialized fabrication may be required- Complex manufacturing process	90% COD removal efficiency- Significantly decreases meMBRsane fouling rate- 95.34%	(Y. Liu et al., 2023)

	activity and the breakdown of EPS		contribution from the micro-electric field	
Platinum wire electrode and conductively modified meMBRsane	High electrical conductivity and stability	High cost, contains mercury and require careful handling	The longevity of platinum is high and has excellent catalytic activity	(Y. Liu et al., 2022)
Carbon fiber cloth cathode membrane with C-Mn-Fe-O catalyst (CCMT)	High removal rates of COD, NH ₄ ⁺ -N, and TP (>90%, >80%, and >65% respectively)	- Requires pretreatment of carbon fiber cloth for catalyst synthesis	Achieves maximum power density of 1358 mW m ⁻³ , 4 times higher than CCMO	(Y. Li, Liu, Yang, & Ren, 2015)
PANI-derived carbon	In-situ generation of ·OH, High removal efficiency of irreversible membrane fouling (77.41%),	Requires activation by -1.0 V bias for optimal performance	Achieves satisfactory wastewater treatment with high COD and NH ₄ ⁺ -N removal efficiencies	(Y. Yang et al., 2022)
Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and Polyethersulfone (PES)	-	-	Significant reduction in membrane fouling observed	(Hasan, Elektorowicz, & Oleszkiewicz, 2012)

Enhanced Pollutants Removal

Figure 2. Schematic Representation of Pollutants Removal Mechanism in eMBRs

Efficient pollutant removal via eMBR involves a multifaceted approach encompassing crucial processes (Figure 2) such as electrochemical mechanisms (electrocoagulation, electro-oxidation, electrophoresis) (Qin et al., 2023), alongside biological degradation and filtration processes (Tognia et al., 2023).

During electrooxidation, reactive species such as ·OH, H₂O₂, and O₃ are produced at the anode

via water electrolysis, initiating the breakdown of chemical bonds within organic pollutants by hydroxyl radicals until complete transformation into CO₂, H₂O, and inorganic ions occurs. (Özyonar & Korkmaz, 2022). There are two primary categories of electrooxidation: direct and indirect oxidation, as outlined by (Qin et al., 2023). In direct oxidation, reactive species are generated independently, without the involvement of additional substances or catalysts (Martínez-Huitle & Panizza, 2018). In contrast, indirect oxidation relies on catalysts like Al³⁺, Fe³⁺, Fe²⁺, Ti⁴⁺, Mn²⁺, and Mn³⁺ to produce reactive species responsible for degrading pollutants (Nair, Soni, & Shah, 2023). This process includes anodic oxidation, involving the degradation of organic pollutants through the oxidation of water at the anode (Y. Jiang et al., 2021) Additionally, cathodic oxidation entails the production of H₂O₂ through the reduction of oxygen at the cathode (Özyonar & Korkmaz, 2022). This procedure confers several notable advantages, such as the effective elimination of contaminants that pose challenges for conventional treatment methodologies (Chaplin, 2018).

COD Removal

Both aerobic membrane bioreactors (AMBRs) and anaerobic membrane bioreactors (AnMBRs) exhibit commendable COD removal

capabilities, but the combination of electrochemical processes with traditional MBRs introduces a distinctive advantage (Ensano et al., 2016). This integration initiates the electrocoagulation process, generating metal ions crucial for neutralizing organic contaminants and fostering the formation of larger flocs, easily separable through membrane filtration within the reactor, resulting in reduced COD in wastewater (Udomkittayachai, Xue, Xiao, Visvanathan, & Tabucanon, 2021). Additionally, electro-oxidation effectively degrades resilient organic pollutants, contributing to a diminished COD rate in wastewater (J. Wang & Wang, 2020). Research outcomes from the integration of electrocoagulation and electrooxidation within eMBRs demonstrate a noteworthy enhancement in COD removal efficiency, reaching 87.7%, coupled with effective mitigation of membrane fouling through the utilization of Fe/SS electron pairs (Ozbey Unal, Dizge, Karagunduz, & Keskinler, 2019). One of the benefits of this approach is its ability to tackle a wide range of organic contaminants effectively. Furthermore, it offers improved efficiency in COD removal and minimizes membrane fouling, leading to an enhanced system.

A comparative evaluation between an electroconductive moving bed membrane bioreactor (EcMB-MBR) and a conventional MBR by (Udomkittayachai et al., 2021), showed higher removal performance of eMBR compared to MBR, with EcMB-MBR demonstrating $97.1 \pm 1.4\%$, $88.8 \pm 4.2\%$, and $99.0 \pm 0.9\%$ removal efficiency for COD, TN, and TP, respectively. Furthermore, integration of an electric current and a conductive membrane in the EcMB-MBR led to substantial mitigation of membrane fouling, particularly enhancing the denitrification process. However, challenges such as increased energy consumption and the need for specialized equipment may hinder widespread adoption of this technology.

Total Nitrogen (TN) Removal

In conventional wastewater treatment, the removal of total nitrogen (TN) typically relies on

bacterial nitrification and denitrification processes within activated sludge. However, in eMBR, TN removal involves both biodegradation and electrochemical (Figure 2) processes (Ibeid & Elektorowicz, 2021). Recent studies have demonstrated that the alternating application of electric current at a density of 12.5 A/m^2 in novel eMBR significantly enhances simultaneous nitrification and denitrification processes, achieving impressive TN and nitrogen (N) removal rates of 90.5% and 83.75%, respectively (Lagum, 2022).

Biodegradation plays a pivotal role in pollutant removal within electrochemical processes combined with membrane technologies (Corpuz et al., 2022). Microorganisms introduced into the bioreactor chamber metabolically degrade organic pollutants, while an applied electric field further enhances biodegradation through reactive species generated at the anode (Fu, Zhang, Jiang, Sun, & Sun, 2023). Moreover, the application of electric current in biological wastewater treatment can stimulate the growth of nitrogen-removing microorganisms crucial for TN removal (Toda et al., 2010). For instance, research on a membrane electro-bioreactor (MEBR, revealed a significant growth of a microbial community dominated by nitrifiers (*Nitrosomonas* spp. and *Nitrobacter* spp.) through intermittent direct current (DC) application. This approach led to high rates of chemical oxygen demand (COD) and nutrient removal (Lagum & Elektorowicz, 2022), offering potential cost savings and energy efficiency in wastewater treatment.

Furthermore, studies on constructed electro-membrane bioreactors (E-MBRs) by (Siddiqua & Faisal, 2021) have demonstrated superior removal performances for COD, ammonium nitrogen (NH_4^+-N), and total phosphorus (TP) compared to conventional MBRs. The findings suggest that E-MBRs can enhance microbial degradation of pollutants in wastewater and have the potential to break down complex pollutant structures effectively. Thus, the integration of electric fields in membrane bioreactors such as eMBRs and E-MBRs promotes microbial growth and enhances TN removal through

efficient biodegradation in wastewater treatment.

Total Phosphorus (TP) Removal

The removal of total phosphorus (TP) in eMBR encompasses various mechanisms, including biological uptake (Figure 2) by polyphosphate-accumulating organisms (POAs) and chemical precipitation via electrochemical dissolution of sacrificial anodes such as aluminum and iron. This holistic approach aligns with the research's focus on exploring efficient phosphorus removal strategies (Cheng & Hong, 2020; Cusick, Ullery, Dempsey, & Logan, 2014).

Electrocoagulation, facilitated by electrode dissolution and subsequent metal hydroxide precipitation, emerges as a promising method for enhancing phosphorus removal efficiency while aiding in floc formation and sedimentation, thus addressing the need for effective wastewater treatment strategies (Ankoliya, Mudgal, Sinha, Patel, & Patel, 2023). Furthermore, within MBR, the electrochemical processes foster an environment conducive to POAs, thereby optimizing nutrient removal mechanisms and contributing to the research's overarching goal (Lagum, 2021). Electrocoagulation's ability to generate coagulants without additional chemicals addresses the drawbacks of chemical-dependent methods, aligning with the research's focus on sustainable and cost-effective wastewater treatment approaches (Kekedy-Nagy et al., 2022). Moreover,

in anaerobic baffled membrane bioreactors (ABMBRs), the integration of electrocoagulation with iron plates not only enhances nutrient removal but also mitigates membrane fouling, offering innovative solutions to wastewater treatment challenges (M. Wu et al., 2021). Despite potential challenges such as membrane fouling, the electrooxidation process in eMBRs shows promise in advanced phosphorus removal, highlighting the research's exploration of cutting-edge treatment methods (Ansari, Hai, Price, Drewes, & Nghiem, 2017; X. Li et al., 2021). Additionally, electrochemical coagulation and electrostatic repulsion in eMBRs demonstrate superior phosphorus removal

efficiency compared to conventional MBRs, showcasing the potential of electrochemical techniques to overcome limitations of traditional methods (Yu, Sun, Zhao, Tian, & Hu, 2023b). While adsorption methods provide an alternative approach to phosphorus removal, considerations such as adsorbent regeneration and disposal must be addressed (Corpuz et al., 2022). Lastly, electrochemical phosphorus removal and recovery in membrane filtration reactors exhibit excellent performance, underscoring the research's emphasis on innovative technologies for efficient nutrient removal, despite potential operational complexities (Ren, Xu, Dai, & Wang, 2023). In conclusion, the diverse approaches explored demonstrate the multifaceted nature of phosphorus removal in wastewater treatment, offering promising avenues for further research and application in practical settings.

Pharmaceuticals Removal

eMBR application is also considered as highly efficient technology for pharmaceuticals removal from wastewater (Ensano et al., 2016). Various electrochemical processes, including electrochemical oxidation, electro-Fenton, and their combinations, along with advanced oxidation processes such as electrochemical oxidation-persulfate (EO-PS), have been extensively investigated within this framework (Ganzenko et al., 2018; A. Wang et al., 2023; W. Yang et al., 2020).

The efficient mechanism of pharmaceutical removal in eMBRs revolves around electron transfer and reactive electrochemical advanced oxidation (EAO) processes (Zhang, Zhou, Yao, Yang, & Zhi, 2021). These processes facilitate the effective removal and mineralization of pharmaceuticals, with direct electrochemical oxidation leading to the oxidation of pharmaceuticals to various valence oxides (Ganiyu, 2016). Moreover, indirect electrochemical oxidation involves strong oxidizing species attacking pharmaceuticals, further contributing to their oxidation to different types of oxides (Calzadilla et al., 2020; Lan, Coetsier, Causserand, & Serrano, 2018).

(C. Wu, Ge, Gu, & Bai, 2023) demonstrated the efficacy of the chronoamperometric method, achieving favorable removal efficiencies, with some cases reaching up to 100%, and revealing significant reductions in the areas of the secondary voltammetry graph. Additionally, a pilot-scale bio-electrochemical treatment coupling microalgae-based high-rate algal pond (HRAP) with electrochemical oxidation (EO) effectively removed pharmaceutical compounds, showcasing higher efficiencies in certain drugs with HRAP, while EO played a crucial role in enhancing the removal of others (Jiménez-Bambague et al., 2023).

(Lozano et al., 2022) highlighted advancements in electrochemical advanced oxidation processes (EAOPs), focusing on anodic oxidation (AO), electro-Fenton (EF), and photoelectro-Fenton (PEF), addressing crucial factors influencing system efficiency and limitations in the degradation of pharmaceuticals in wastewater treatment. However, the study acknowledged economic and energy efficiency challenges associated with scaling up light-induced

processes like PEF and photoelectrochemical oxidation (PEC).

Conversely, (Feier, Florea, Cristea, & Săndulescu, 2018) emphasized the evolving landscape of electrochemical methods for pharmaceutical detection and removal, emphasizing advancements in sensor development, innovative detection strategies, and nanomaterial applications, while also acknowledging existing challenges such as harmonized legislation and improvements in detection sensitivity and selectivity.

Overall, these studies underscore the potential efficacy of electrochemical methods in pharmaceutical removal, providing nuanced insights into enhanced pollutant removal within eMBRs. However, they also highlight the need for further investigations to address specific limitations and optimize the efficiency of these processes. A brief overview of some studies investigating the utilization of electrochemical methodologies in eMBR technology for pharmaceutical removal are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Examples of Successful Research Endeavors Investigating the Efficacy of eMBRs for the Removal of Pollutants from Wastewater

Type of reactor	Targeted wastewater	Removal efficiency and performance	References
sandwich-type composite anodic meMBRsane (EC-An MBR)	High solid biowaste-containing wastewater	98.3% COD r, 97.9% Total coliforms, 12.8% increase in methane yield	(Han et al., 2023)
Three-chamber electrochemical meMBRsane bioreactor (EMBRs) with a microbial fuel cell (MFC)	Synthetic wastewater and 20% landfill leachate (LFL)	BOD _{5,20} : 98 ± 1% 86 ± 5% COD, 79 ± 2% N-NH ₄ , 72 ± 6% DOC, 43 ± 3% TN	(Pierangeli, Raggio, Benassi, Gregoracci, & Subtil, 2021)
Electroconductive bed meMBRsane bioreactor (EcB-MBR)	Municipal wastewater	98.5 ± 1.0% COD, 98.9 ± 0.7% TP, 48.5 ± 14.9% TN, Selected PPCPs Varying from 1.8% to 36% improvement	(Sutthiwanit, He, Hong, Guerrero-Cruz, & Xue, 2023)
Anaerobic electrochemical meMBRsane bioreactor (AnEMBRs)	Antibiotic-containing wastewater, specifically with chlortetracycline (CTC) concentrations ranging from 2.5 to 45 mg/L	≥96% COD, 100% CTC, decrease in turbidity and TMP	(Z.-H. Li, Yuan, Yang, Wang, & Sheng, 2022)
Electrochemical MeMBRsane Bioreactor (EMBRs)	Real municipal wastewater containing PPCPs (Pharmaceuticals and Personal Care Products)	92.18% COD, 97.44% NH ₄ ⁺ -N, 14 PPCPs (fluoroquinolones, macrolides, anti-inflammatory drugs) removal	(M. Chen et al., 2020)

Electric Field MeMBRSane Bioreactor (EMBRs) using reduced graphene oxide/polypyrrole ceramic meMBRSane (rGO/PPy CM)	Mariculture wastewater	84.99% TOC, 85.98% NH ⁴⁺ -N, total resistance reduced by 8.12% to 62.48%	(R. Wang et al., 2023)
air-cathode bio-electrochemically assisted osmotic meMBRSane bioreactor	Synthetic municipal wastewater	93.08% TN, current production of 110.67 A/m ³	(Y. Wu et al., 2022)
Electro-MBR	High-strength ammonia leachate (initial concentration of 124 ± 4 mg NH ₄ ⁺ -N L ⁻¹)	Ammonia nitrogen removal: 99.8% - Total organic carbon (TOC) removal: 38% - Total phosphorus (P _{tot}) removal: 99.0	(Roy et al., 2020)
(Electrochemical Membrane Bioreactor) with Fe anode and membrane cathode	Municipal wastewater or synthetic water simulating municipal wastewater	Membrane fouling mitigation, Reduction in EPS, Microbial species diversity: Increased, enhancing the adaptability of biochemical systems to water quality variations.	(Yu, Sun, Zhao, Tian, & Hu, 2023a)
ICME/electro-biocarriers-MBR system	Livestock wastewater	COD removal: 76.0%, TSS removal: 100%, Antibiotic removal: 86.4%, NH ₄ ⁺ -N removal: 91.1%, ARGs reduction	(F. Chen et al., 2022)
SMEBR and Conventional	Municipal wastewater	Average removal of phosphorus: 99%, ammonia: 99%, COD: 92%	(Hasan et al., 2012)

Membrane Fouling Mitigation

Membrane fouling, characterized by the accumulation of various foulants such as EPS, colloids, soluble organics, microorganisms, and dissolved organic compounds on the membrane surface or within its pores, poses a significant challenge to the performance of MBRs (Arefi-Oskoui, Khataee, Safarpour, Orooji, & Vatanpour, 2019). This fouling leads to reduced permeate flux and increased transmembrane pressure (TMP), thereby hindering the efficiency of MBR systems. Electrochemical techniques integrated with conventional MBRs have emerged as a promising approach to mitigate membrane fouling and enhance filtration efficiency, prolonging membrane lifespan and producing high-quality effluent (J.-P. Chen, Yang, Zhou, & Wang, 2007).

In the electrocoagulation process, the application of electric current at the electrodes induces the production of coagulants such as Al³⁺ and Fe³⁺ (Figure 3) leading to the formation of flocs with higher settling velocities.

Figure 3. Schematic Representation of Membrane Fouling Alleviation Mechanisms in eMBRs

These flocs effectively reduce the concentration of suspended solids and colloidal matters in wastewater, thus minimizing their attachment to the membrane surface and mitigating membrane fouling (Manica et al., 2021). Research on a novel

electrocoagulation membrane cathode reactor (ECMCR) demonstrated significant membrane fouling mitigation, reducing TMP by 84.6% compared to conventional MBR filtration. This approach forms a porous cake layer and enhances water flux through a combination of electrocoagulation and electrokinetic effects in membrane technology (Yu et al., 2022). Similarly, in AnMBR, the electrocoagulation process led to a 50% reduction in TMP and an increase in floc size and porosity, resulting in significant membrane fouling mitigation (Deng et al., 2022).

Electroosmosis offers another effective method for membrane fouling mitigation by removing bound water from sludge flocs through the application of an electric field. This process induces migration of water molecules towards the cathode, reducing interaction forces between water molecules and sludge particles, resulting in drier sludge and reduced fouling (Ping & Guohua, 2018). Research on an AnOMEBR demonstrated a 26% reduction in the concentration of soluble microbial products and enhanced electrostatic repulsion between the charged membrane surface and foulants, leading to significantly lower cake layer thickness compared to conventional AnMBRs (Xu et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the production of H₂ gas through electrochemical processes inhibits foulant adhesion to the membrane surface and facilitates their removal by suspending pollutants and making them more available to microorganisms (Yu et al., 2023b).

Electrophoresis also plays a crucial role in preventing membrane fouling by directing charged particles away from the membrane surface. Utilizing two conductive membranes can enhance repulsion of foulants and improve membrane permeability while in-situ bubbles generated disrupt surface fouling. However, caution must be exercised regarding the negative impact of excessive bubbles and electrolyte concentration on membrane performance (Liu et al., 2021).

In summary, electrochemical techniques offer promising avenues for mitigating membrane fouling in MBRs, encompassing various mechanisms such as electrocoagulation, electroosmosis, and electrophoresis. These approaches hold significant potential for enhancing the efficiency and longevity of membrane-based wastewater treatment systems. Introduces some example efforts for mitigating membrane fouling by eMBR technology and their efficiency.

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	concentrations ranging from 2.5 to 45 mg/L		
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Electro-MBR	High-strength ammonia leachate (initial concentration of 124 ± 4 mg NH ₄ ⁺ -N L ⁻¹)	Ammonia nitrogen removal: 99.8% - Total organic carbon (TOC) removal: 38% - Total phosphorus (P _{tot}) removal: 99.0	(Roy et al., 2020)
(Electrochemical Membrane Bioreactor) with Fe anode and membrane cathode	Municipal wastewater or synthetic water simulating municipal wastewater	Membrane fouling mitigation, Reduction in EPS, Microbial species diversity: Increased, enhancing the adaptability of biochemical systems to water quality variations.	(Yu et al., 2023a)
ICME/electro-biocarriers-MBR system	Livestock wastewater	COD removal: 76.0%, TSS removal: 100%, Antibiotic removal: 86.4%, NH ₄ ⁺ -N removal: 91.1%, ARGs reduction	(F. Chen et al., 2022)
SMEBR and Conventional	Municipal wastewater	Average removal of phosphorus: 99%, ammonia: 99%, COD: 92%	(Hasan et al., 2012)

Operating parameters of eMBRs

HRT and SRT

Hydraulic retention time (HRT) and solid retention time (SRT) are vital parameters in eMBR operation, impacting treatment efficiency (Bao et al., 2023; Y. Z. Wang et al., 2015). Optimizing HRT enhances pollutant removal and operational efficiency by extending microorganism-pollutant contact time (Asif et al., 2020). Electrocoagulation in eMBRs increases contaminant retention by promoting aggregation and settling of particles, enhancing treatment efficiency (Bao et al., 2023). Altering HRT significantly affects treatment efficiency in electrochemical wastewater processes

(Moazzem et al., 2020). For instance, adjusting HRT in electroactive microbial biofilm reactors influences substrate degradation and pH stability, improving overall performance (Mohanakrishna et al., 2020).

Similarly, HRT plays a crucial role in electrooxidation processes, with longer HRTs enhancing total organic carbon (TOC) removal and process performance (Liang, You, Yuan, & Yuan, 2021). SRT also influences system performance, with longer SRT promoting biofilm formation and enhancing microbial activity on bioelectrode surfaces (Y. Wang, 2020). This fosters a diverse microbial population capable of efficient pollutant degradation and electron transfer, leading to

higher current densities and energy recovery efficiency in eMBR system.

Hence, HRT and SRT are pivotal in optimizing pollutant removal and energy recovery in electrochemical processes, defining the optimal conditions for effective wastewater treatment in EMBR technology.

Current Density (CD)

Quantifying the electric current passing through a unit area, correlates positively with voltage, leading to its frequent utilization by researchers as a representative measure of the electrical characteristics of the entire reactor. According to the principles of three-dimensional electrochemistry, the power supply induces particle polarization, thereby influencing the system's energy consumption [93]. Studies indicate that as the current density gradually approaches an optimum value, degradation efficiency tends to increase. Conversely, exceeding this optimal current density leads to a decline in degradation efficiency [94]. This phenomenon arises from competing reactions, notably involving the anode's oxygen evolution, at high current densities.

Increased current density induces increased microbial activity, particularly in bacteria associated with electrochemical processes, such as *Anaeromusa* and *Lactococcus*. These microbes are able to break down organic foulants that are attached to the membrane surface, like polysaccharides and proteins. In addition, increased current density causes inorganic ions, like Ca^{2+} , to migrate away from the membrane surface, which stops deposition and lessens fouling. These findings imply that the system's self-generated micro-electric field and current actively contribute to the breakdown of both organic and inorganic membrane fouling. As a result, the importance of current density in improving overall system performance is emphasized. Consequently, regular monitoring of current density is imperative to sustain high pollutant degradation and increase in fouling within the bioreactor.

Direct Current (DC)

Direct current (DC) in eMBRs is the continuous flow of electric charge in a single direction playing significant role in enhancement of membrane performance pollutants removal performance of eMBR by promoting electrokinetic processes, improving membrane fouling control, and optimizing biological treatment efficiency (Hou et al., 2019). DC application, particularly in the form of intermittent electrification with optimal operating conditions, significantly influences the performance of an eMBR as investigated by (Mao et al., 2024). The study also emphasizes that DC enhances membrane fouling control, extends system run time, and improves the efficiency of contaminant removal in simulated domestic wastewater, showcasing the positive impact of DC on eMBR technology with polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membranes. (B. Jiang et al., 2020) has shown that DC in eMBR significantly mitigates membrane fouling by influencing the membrane permeability, total membrane resistance, zeta potential, and EPS content. The study further demonstrates that the increase in voltage enhances electrostatic repulsion between sludge particles, reduces membrane fouling rate, and leads to a decrease in AHLs (acyl-homoserine lactones) concentration, contributing to effective membrane antifouling. DC in an eMBR significantly influence the degradation of pollutants, membrane fouling rate, and EPS content, and can be considered as an important parameter influencing the effective removal of pollutants in wastewater treatment (S. Shi et al., 2019).

Generally, studies highlight the multifaceted impact of direct current (DC) application in eMBRs, offering a promising avenue for enhancing pollutant removal efficiency and mitigating membrane fouling in wastewater treatment processes.

pH

The pH level is a critical factor in eMBR processes, with varying effects depending on the specific method utilized. In electrocoagulation, pH impacts the electrostatic field and the

efficiency of metal hydroxide floc formation, while in electrooxidation, it influences the production of reactive oxygen species and pollutant degradation efficiency (Fu et al., 2023). Therefore, optimizing pH according to each process is essential to ensure higher treatment performance in eMBRs. Alkaline conditions can enhance the oxygen evolution reaction at the anode, leading to lower degradation efficiency due to interference with catalytic oxidation reactions of contaminants (Samarghandi et al., 2021). Additionally, the ionization of metal elements such as Fe occurs under acidic conditions to form the Fenton system, further highlighting the significant impact of pH on eMBR performance (Teng et al., 2021).

Research by (Mohanakrishna et al., 2020) has confirmed the importance of pH in eMBR performance, noting that pH levels between 6 and 8.5 are conducive to bioelectricity generation, while levels exceeding 8.5 can have detrimental effects due to byproduct formation. Maintaining appropriate pH levels in Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) is crucial for successful substrate breakdown and power generation. Furthermore, pH can significantly influence microbial activity, substrate availability, and membrane fouling, with the optimal pH range for degrading organic pollutants and minimizing fouling considered to be between 6.5 and 7.5 (Bao et al., 2023).

Discussion

While eMBRs present numerous benefits for improving pollutant removal and addressing membrane fouling, they also pose certain challenges that warrant further exploration to achieve optimal wastewater treatment conditions with enhanced efficiency. One notable issue is the costliness of electrode materials, particularly concerning scalability (Y. Li et al., 2019). Additionally, the limited lifespan of electrodes presents a challenge, necessitating timely replacements and resulting in additional procurement expenses (M. Chen et al., 2023). Moreover, limitations in the utilization of electrophoresis for membrane fouling prevention have been identified, highlighting

concerns regarding the adverse effects of excessive bubbles and elevated electrolyte concentration on membrane performance, as revealed in research by (Lie Liu et al., 2021). These constraints underscore the critical need for precise control over bubble generation and electrolyte levels to maintain continuous reactor efficiency when employing electrophoretic methods. These issues underscore the vital importance of developing cost-effective and durable electrode solutions, particularly in scaling up settings of eMBR for wastewater treatment. While eMBR shows promise in advancement of pollutants removal and membrane fouling mitigation, challenges such as; high costs of electrode materials specially when considering scalability (Y. Li et al., 2019), short life of electrode materials (M. Chen et al., 2023) and limitations in the utilization of electrophoresis for membrane fouling prevention (Lie Liu et al., 2021) require further investigations to develop cost-effective and durable solutions especially in scaling up wastewater treatment.

Conclusion

The review of electrochemical and MBR technologies underscores significant findings. Integration of electrochemical processes with MBRs, forming eMBRs, enhances pollutant removal, reduces membrane fouling, and improves operational stability. Advanced electrode materials, such as stainless-steel mesh (SSM-100m) and Ti/RuO₂-Sb₂O₄, enhance efficiency in electrochemical oxidation. Despite promising outcomes, challenges remain, including electrode cost, limitations of electrophoresis for fouling prevention, and the necessity to optimize operational parameters (HRT, SRT, CD, DC, pH). Ongoing research is vital to address these challenges, optimize efficiency, and explore resource recovery in eMBRs. While eMBRs exhibit potential for wastewater treatment, further investigation and optimization are essential to address the identified limitations and challenges.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Tongji University's College of Environmental Science and Engineering and the UNEP-Tongji Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development for their assistance and resources. Furthermore, the authors thank the School of Environmental Science and Engineering at Tongji University for their contributions to this research.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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